

MEHNATNI MUHOFAZA QILISHNING RIVOJLANISH TARIXIY BOSQICHLARINI O'RGANISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada, mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanishi bosqichlari va tarixiy adabiyotlarda sohaning tahlillari haqida fikr mulohazalar keltirilgan. Maqola mehnat muhoazasi va texnika xavfsizligi yunalishlari talablari, mehnat muhofazasi va xavfsizlik mutaxassislari hamda keng izlanuvchilar uchun muljallangan.

Kalit so'zlar va iboralar: “Xavfsizlik. mehnatni muhofaza qilish, sanoat, tog`-kon ishlari, xavfli va zararli faktor. Ish vaqti, dam olish vaqti, Xalqaro mehnat tashkiloti, Xalqaro sog`liqni saqlash tashkiloti”.

STUDY OF HISTORICAL STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF LABOR PROTECTION

Abstract. This article reviews the stages of labor protection development and analyzes of the field in historical literature. The article is intended for the requirements of labor protection and technical safety directions, labor protection and safety specialists, and general readers.

Key words and phrases: "Safety. labor protection, industry, mining, dangerous and harmful factor. Working time, rest time, International Labor Organization, International Health Organization".

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ИСТОРИЧЕСКИХ ЭТАПОВ РАЗВИТИЯ ОХРАНЫ ТРУДА

Аннотация. В статье представлены этапы развития охраны труда и проведен анализ данной области в исторической литературе. Статья предназначена для требований направлений охраны труда и технической безопасности, специалистов по охране труда и технике безопасности, а также широкого круга читателей.

Ключевые слова и фразы: «Безопасность. охрана труда, промышленность, горнодобывающая промышленность, опасный и вредный фактор. Рабочее время, время отдыха, Международная организация труда, Международная организация здравоохранения».

KIRISH. Insoniyatning uzoq o'tmish hayotiy tajribasi har qanday faoliyat potensial xavfga ega ekanligini tasdiqlaydi. Albatta, bu tasdiq aksiomaviy xususiyatga egadir. Vaholanki, ishlab chiqarish sharoitida xavf darajasini boshqarish hamda kamaytirish ham mumkin. Lekin qanday holatda bo'lmasin, absolyut xavfsizlikka erishib bo'lmaydi.

Xavfsizlik – ma'lum darajada xavf tug'ilishi bartaraf etilgan faoliyat holati, ya'ni faoliyatni amalga oshirishdagi asosiy maqsadlardan biridir [1] [2].

Mehnatni muhofaza qilish – ishlab chiqarishdagi mehnat xavfsizligini ta'minlashga qaratilgan vositalar usullar majmuidir. Demak, insonning mehnat xavfsizligini ta'minlash birinchi navbatda uning mehnat faoliyati jarayonini va uni amalga oshirishda yuzaga keladigan xavfli faktorlarni o'rganishni talab etadi. Shu sababli, inson mehnat faoliyatining xavfsizligini ta'minlash bo'yicha tadqiqot ishlari eramizdan oldingi 384–322-yillarda ijod qilgan Aristotel, eramizdan oldingi 460–377-yillarda yashagan Gippokrat asarlarida ham uchraydi [1] [2].

Tiklanish davrining buyuk, taniqli olimi Paratsels (1493–1541-y.) tog' ishlarini bajarishda yuzaga keladigan xavfli faktorlarni o'rganib chiqqan. U o'z asarlarida: «Barcha moddalar zahardir va barcha moddalar dori-darmon hamdir. Faqat bir me'yor ushbu moddani za-harga aylantirsa, ikkinchi me'yor esa uni dori-darmonga aylantiradi», deb yozadi. Nemis olimi Agrikol (1494–1555-y.) o'zining «Tog' ishlari haqida» *nomli* asarida, shuningdek, italyan olimi Ramatstsin (1633–1714-y.), rus olimi M. V. Lomonosov (1711–1765-y.) o'z asarlarida mehnat muhofazasi masalalariga katta e'tibor qaratgan [2].

XIX asrda sanoatni intensiv rivojlanishi natijasida mehnat muhofazasi muammolari bo'yicha ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borgan bir qancha olimlar yetishib chiqdi. Jumladan, V.L.Kirpichev (1845–1913-y.), A.A.Bess (1857–1930-y.), D.P.Nikolskiy (1855–1918-y.), V.A.Levitskiy (1867–1936y.), A.A.Skochinslay (1874–1960-y.), S.I.Kaplun (1897– 1943-y.) shular jumlasidandir. Yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek, mehnat xavfsizligini ta'minlash qadimgi davrdan hozirgi kungacha inson faoliyatining muhim tomonlaridan biri hisoblanib kelindi. Shu sababli «Mehnatni muhofaza qilish» mustaqil fan sifatida shakllandi va o'z nazariyasiga, uslubiga hamda tamoyillariga ega bo'ldi. Shu bilan bir qatorda «Mehnatni muhofaza qilish» fani muhandislik psixologiyasi, psixofiziologiya, mehnat fiziologiyasi, mehnat gigiyenasi, antropometriya, ergonomika, texnikaviy estetika kabi fanlarning yutuqlariga asoslanadi. Ushbu fanlar bir-biridan tadqiqot qilinadigan yoki o'rganiladigan obyektlarining turi, ya'ni «inson-mashina», «inson-muhit», «inson-mashina muhit» tizimlari bilan farq qiladi.

Birinchi turdagi tizimlar qonuniyatlarini muhandislik psixologiyasi, psixofiziologiya, mehnat fiziologiyasi o'rgansa, «inson-muhit» tizimi qonuniyatlarini mehnat gigiyenasi o'rganadi. «Insonmashina-muhit» qonuniyatlari esa ergonomikaning asosiy tatbiq obyekti hisoblanadi.

Lekin, real ishlab chiqarish sharoitida barcha turdagi bog'lanishlar bir vaqtda yuzaga keladi va shu sababli inson o'z mehnat faoliyatida bir necha omillar bilan bog'lanadi, o'zaro ta'sirda bo'ladi. Shu sababli, ishlab chiqarish sharoitidagi umumlashgan xavfli va zararli faktorlarning inson sog'ligi va mehnat qobiliyatiga birgalikdagi ta'sirini alohida mustaqil fan – «Mehnatni muhofaza qilish» fani o'rganadi [3].

Tadqiqot metodlari. Tadqiqot jarayonida ilmiy va o'quv-uslubiy adabiyotlar tahlili, pedagogik-tarixiy kuzatuv, umumlashtirish, metodlaridan foydalanildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari va muhokamalar. XV – XVI asrlarda tog'-kon metallurgiyasi sohasining jadal rivojlanishi natijasida og'ir mehnat sharoitlari, konchilikdagi chang natijasida vujudga keladigan kasbiy kasalliklar to'g'risida ilmiy ishlar ko'paya bordi. Bu Agrikol va Paraselsaning ishlari hisoblanadi [1].

Antik va o'rta asrlar buyuk olimlarning harakatlari kasbiy faoliyat bilan bog'liq kasalliklarning kelib chiqishini o'rganuvchi alohida fanning vujudga kelishiga zamin yaratdi.

Fanning asoschisi haqli ravishda italyan vrachi, professor, Paduan universiteti rektori Bernardino Ramassini (1633 – 1714 y) hisoblanadi. Uning «Hunarmandlarning kasalliklari to‘g‘risida fikrlar» deb nomlangan kitobida turli sohalaridagi mehnat gigienasi masalalari tizimli tahlil qilingan, kasblar bilan bog‘liq kasalliklarning klinik ta‘rifi keltirilgan fundamental asar hisoblanadi. Olim mazkur asarni yozish uchun 50 yildan ortiq fakt yiqqan. U feodal tuzumdan ilk kapitalizmga o‘tish davrida hunarmandlar, manufakturalardagi ishchilarning yashash va mehnat sharoitlarini kuzatgan [1].

Shuningdek, M. V. Lomonosov (1711 – 1765) tog‘-kon ishlarida mehnat muhofazasiga oid, F.F. Erisman (1842 – 1915 y) mehnat gigienasi to‘g‘risida «Jismoniy va aqliy mehnat gigienasi» nomli asarlarida mazkur masalaga atroflicha to‘xtalgan [1].

Ilmiy-texnik taraqqiyot ishlab chiqarish sohasiga keskin yangiliklarni olib kirmoqda. Jarayonda mehnat qurollari va predmeti shakli o‘zgarib bormoqda. Bu esa, o‘z o‘rnida, mehnat sharoitlarga ta‘sir o‘tkazyapti.

Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning keyingi rivojlanish bosqichlari:

1-bosqich – 1900 yilning boshlarida (1903) quyidagi qoidalarni o‘z ichiga olgan dastur qabul qilinishidan boshlangan:

- 8 soatli ish kuni joriy qilish;
- haftada bir kun dam olish;
- 15 yoshgacha bo‘lgan bolalar mehnatining taqiqlanishi;
- sog‘liq uchun zararli bo‘lgan tarmoqlarda ayollar mehnatini bartaraf etish;
- bayram kunlarida dam olish;
- xodimlarga shikast yetkazilganda fabrikaning javobgarligi;
- bepul tibbiy yordam ko‘rsatish;
- kasal bo‘lganda maoshining saqlanishi.

2-bosqich – qoidalarni amaliyotga tatbiq etish.

Mazkur bosqichga quyidagi yaqqol misollarni keltirish mumkin:

11.11.17 y. – 8 soatli ish kuni, 48 soatli ish haftasi haqida Dekret qabul qilingan.

O‘sha vaqtning o‘zida quyidagilar o‘rnatildi:

- mehnat qilish vaqtidagi tanaffuslar;
- zararli mehnat sharoitlarida mehnat haftasining qisqartirilishi; – yer osti va ish vaqtdan tashqari ishlarda ayollar va o‘smirlar mehnatining taqiqlanishi;
- o‘smirlar uchun 6 soatlik ish kuni joriy qilinishi.

18.05.18 y. – Mehnat inspeksiyasi tashkil etildi (mehnat xavfsizligini ta‘minlash bo‘yicha).

1918 y. Mehnat qonunlarining Kodeksi qabul qilindi (KZOT)

3-bosqich – ishlab chiqarishdagi zararli omillar o‘rganildi va zarar ta‘sirini yo‘qotish bo‘yicha tavsiyalar qidirildi.

1929 y. – Kasb kasalliklarini o‘rganish ilmiy tadqiqot instituti tashkil etildi.

1932 y. – Alohida og‘ir va zararli ishlar ro‘yxati tasdiqlandi.

4-bosqich – mehnat sharoitlarini yaxshilash bosqichi, tashkilotlarning rejalariga mehnatni muhofaza qilish tadbirlarining kiritilishi (50-yillarning oxirlari).

5-bosqich – Zamonaviy (hozirgi kundagi).

Olti kunlik ish haftasida har kungi ishning muddati 7 soatdan, 5 kunlik ish haftasida esa 8 soatdan etib belgilandi, ish vaqtining normal muddati haftasiga 40 soatdan osmasligi 16 dan 18 yoshgacha bo‘lganlarga – haftasiga 36 soatdan; 15 dan 16 yoshgacha bo‘lganlarga – haftasiga 24 soatdan oshmaydigan qilib belgilandi [1] [2] [3].

Xulosa. Mehnatni muhofaza qilish (yoki ish xavfsizligi) ahamiyati dunyoda, kasb-hunar sohasida va jamiyat uchun juda muhimdir. Quyidagi sabablar bilan mehnatni muhofaza qilishning ahamiyati kuzatiladi:

1. Hayotni muhofaza qilish: Mehnat xavfsizligi, ishchilarni har qanday xavf va zararli holatlardan himoya qiladi. Bu, har bir kishining hayoti va sog‘ligi uchun muhimdir.

2. Ish faoliyatini o‘rganish: Mehnatni muhofaza qilish tashqi yo‘nalishlarni tushunish, xavfsizlikni ta‘minlash, zararlar va risklarni kamaytirishni o‘rganishni o‘zi bilan kelayotgan bo‘ladi.

3. Ish joylari va korxonalari uchun maqsadli: Sifatli mehnatni muhofaza qilish, ish joylari va korxonalari uchun xavfsiz va foydali ortiqcha foydalanishni ta‘minlaydi. Bu, ishlab chiqarishning yo‘qotilmasligini va ishlar yuritilishini ta‘minlaydi.

4. O‘qitish va bilim olish: Mehnat xavfsizligi ta‘limi va amaliyotlari o‘qitish, xavfsiz ish ko‘rish va shaxsiy zimmasizlikni o‘rganish imkoniyatlarini beradi.

5. Davlat siyosati: Hukumatlar uchun, xavfsizlik so‘zini olishning ahamiyati bor.

Xavfsizlik va muhofaza qilish siyosatlarini insonlarning sog‘ligi, ekologiya va jamoatning umumiy xavfsizligi uchun juda muhimdir.

6. Boshqarish va tartib boshqarish: Mehnat xavfsizligi ta‘mini, ish joylari va korxonalari uchun boshqaruvchilar uchun ham muhimdir. Bu, faoliyatni boshqarishni osonlashtiradi va ishlab chiqarishni o‘rganish imkoniyatlarini ta‘minlaydi.

7. Ishlab chiqarishni o‘zgartirish: Mehnat xavfsizligi ta‘mini, ishlab chiqarishning barqarorligini oshirish, zararlar va ta‘silarni kamaytirish va ishchilarga qulay sharoitlar yaratishga yordam beradi.

8. Yong‘in va elektr xavfsizligi: ishlab chiqarish va inson hayotida yong‘in xavfsizligi, elektr xavfsizligi tadbirlari, o‘qitish va qayta tayyorlash. Texnologik xavfsizlik talablarini yong‘in va elektr xavfsizligiga moslash.[8]

Mehnatni muhofaza qilish, barcha taraflar uchun foydalidir va hamma uchun muhimdir.

Bu, sog‘liging o‘zi bilan keladi, ish joylari va korxonalari uchun foydalidir va jamiyatni sog‘liqni va xavfsizlikni o‘zgartirishga olib keladi.

Sohani rivojlanishi fan texnikaning rivojlanishi, ishlab chiqarishga kiritilayotgan yangi zamonaviy uskunalarning tasnifi, Xalqaro sog‘liqni saqlash tashkiloti, Xalqaro mehnat tashkiloti, Xalqaro kasaba uyushmasi federatsiyasi uyushmasi tavsiya va xulosalari asosida yangi taraqqiyot bosqichiga o‘tib ulgurdi. Yuqoridagilarni inobatga olib mehnat monosabati ishtirokchilarini zamonaviy usullarda mehnat muhofazasi va taenika xavfsiuzligiga o‘qitish va yo‘riqnomalardan o‘tkazishning zamonaviy usullarini tatbiq etish lozim[5] [6] [7]. Insonning mehnat xavfsizligini ta‘minlashda ilmiy-nazariy izlanishlar asosida vujudga kelgan qonunlar, nizomlar, standartlar, ko‘rsatmalar, qoidalar va sanitartexnik me‘yorlar hamda ularni o‘rganish bo‘yicha uzluksiz ta‘lim-tarbiya tizimini vujudga keltirish, uni rivojlantirish muhim o‘rin tutadi.

REFERENCES

1. Xidirova Dildora, Muradov Sirojiddin. O‘zbekiston respublikasi hududida seysmoaktiv hududlar va zilzilaning xavfliligi//Innovative Development in Educational Activities. 2024. 167-172
2. Muradov S. ЭCONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PROFITS IN THE FIELD OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1239-1245.
3. Мурадов, С. (2024). PRINCIPLES OF ENSURING THE SAFETY OF USING LIFTING CRANES IN CONSTRUCTION-ASSEMBLY WORKS. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(2), 933–939. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10684936>
4. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН учитель-стажер. Каршинский инженерно-экономический институт кафедры «Охрана труда и техника безопасности» Республики Узбекистан. (2024). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10684166>
5. Muradov Sirojiddin. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning tashkiliy-psixologik asoslaridagi mavjud muammolar//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”. 2023. 133-137.
6. Muradov Sirojiddin. Mehnat sharoitlari va muhitini “kaizen” usuli yordamida takomillashtirishning innovatsion yechimlari//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”.2023. 249-253.
7. Muradov Sirojiddin. Mehnatni muhofaza qilish sohasida yuk ortish va tushirish ishlaridagi yukchilar uchun ishlarning xavfsizligi kategori va qoidalari tahlili//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”. 2023. 232-242
8. Muradov Sirojiddin. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanish tarixiy bosqichlarini o‘rganish//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”. 2023. 243-248
9. Muradov Sirojiddin. Sanoat korxonalarini rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning ahamiyati//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”. 2023. 146-150
10. Muradov Sirojiddin. Xavfli sanoat korxonalarida ishchilarni xavfli gaz va zaxarli moddalar ta’siridan himoya qilishga qaratilgan inovatsion yechimlar//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”. 2023. 402-405
11. Muradov Sirojiddin Husan o‘g‘li. Sanoat korxonalarini rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning ahamiyati// Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. 2023/10/26. 180-183
12. Мурадов Сирожиддин. Определение отдыха и отпусков на основании нового трудового кодекса// Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. 2023/10/26. 17-21

13. MURADOV SIROJIDDIN HUSAN O'G'LI. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanish tarixiy bosqichlarini o'rganish// Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. 2023/10/26. 8-16
14. Muradov, S. (2023). ISHLAB CHIQRISHDAGI AVARIYALARNI O'RGANISH VA TAHLIL QILISH. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(16), 474–477. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/5015>
15. Muradov Sirojiddin. Ishlab chiqarishdagi avariyaalarni o'rganish va tahlil qilish// Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(16), 474–477.
16. Muradov S. ISHLAB CHIQRISHDAGI AVARIYALARNI O'RGANISH VA TAHLIL QILISH //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 16. – C. 474-477.
17. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 42-47.
18. Sultonova D. N., & Siddiqova M. A. qizi. (2023). COLOR SCHEME IN THE FORMATION OF THE ARTISTIC ENVIRONMENT OF THE INTERIOR OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL CENTERS. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(14), 109–115. Retrieved from <https://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/4394>
19. Sultonova D. N., qizi Siddiqova M. A. COLOR SCHEME IN THE FORMATION OF THE ARTISTIC ENVIRONMENT OF THE INTERIOR OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL CENTERS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 14. – C. 109-115.
20. Muradov Sirojiddin Husan o'g'li, Xakimov Xurshid Hamidulla o'g'li, & Siddiqova Madinabonu Asatilla qizi. (2021). NEW INNOVATIVE ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS OF SIGNALIZATION AND SECURITY SYSTEMS. European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 2, 28-30. Retrieved from <http://www.ejlss.indexedresearch.org/index.php/ejlss/article/view/13>
21. Muradov S. H. o'g'li, & Zayniyev, U. U. o'g'li. (2023). PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(14), 116–119. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/4395>
22. Muradov Sirojiddin Husan o'g'li, Zayniyev Ulfat Utkir o'g'li. PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES. Educational Research in Universal Sciences. 2023-11
23. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 42-47.
24. Muradov Sirojiddin; Egamberdiyev Umurzoq. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD//International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 42-47.

25. Husan o'g'li M. S., Hamidulla o'g'li X. X. Siddiqova Madinabonu Asatilla qizi. NEW INNOVATIVE ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS OF SIGNALIZATION AND SECURITY SYSTEMS //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – 2021. – T. 2. – C. 28-30.
26. Husan o'g'li M. S., Shavkat o'g'li E. D. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – C. 11-17.
27. Muradov S. H. o'g'li, & Egamov, D. S. o'g'li. (2023). INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(14), 340–342. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/4443>
28. O'G E. L. A. A. et al. PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HYGIENE BASIS OF HUMAN LABOR ACTIVITY //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 11.
29. MURADOV SIROJIDDIN HUSAN O'G'LI; ESHPO'LATOV AZIZBEK ADHAM O'G'LI. PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HYGIENE BASIS OF HUMAN LABOR ACTIVITY// International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management.2023.266-273.
30. Rakhimov, O. D., and S. H. Muradov. "Digitalization of Instructions on Labor Protection and Safety Techniques." European journal of life safety and stability (EJLSS) 24 (2022): 80-86.
31. O.D. Rakhimov, Muradov S.H. Digitalization of Instructions on Labor Protection and Safety Techniques. // European journal of life safety and stability (EJLSS). 2022. №24. P.80-86.
32. O'G'LI M. S. H. ANALYSIS OF “MEASURES TO ENSURE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY IN THE FIELD OF CARGO TRANSPORTATION AND LOADING.” //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 9.
33. MURADOV SIROJIDDIN HUSAN O'G'LI. ANALYSIS OF “MEASURES TO ENSURE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY IN THE FIELD OF CARGO TRANSPORTATION AND LOADING.”// INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT. Vol. 2 No. 9 (2023). 127-133
34. ЎҒЛИ Р. Х. Ф., СИРОЖИДДИН М. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 10.
35. ЎҒЛИ, РАЖАБОВ ХУРШИД ФАХРИДДИН, and МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН. "ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН." International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management 2.10 (2023).
36. ЎҒЛИ, Р. Х. Ф., & СИРОЖИДДИН, М. (2023). ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН. International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management, 2(10).

37. Rayimkulov A., Murodov S. Some Issues of Safety in the Use of Tower Cranes Used in Construction Projects //JournalNX. – С. 301-308.
38. Rayimkulov A., Murodov S. Some Issues of Safety in the Use of Tower Cranes Used in Construction Projects //JournalNX. – С. 301-308.
39. Мурадов, Сирожиддин. "ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 2.5 (2023).
40. Мурадов С. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5.
41. Мурадов, С. (2023). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(5).
42. Raximov O.D, Muradov S.H. SANOAT KORXONALARI RAHBARI VA MUTAXASSISLARINI MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI BO‘YICHA O‘QITISH VA BILIMLARINI SINOVDAN O‘TKAZISHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH. MONOGRAFIYA.2023.1-96
43. Raximov O.D, Muradov S.H. SANOAT KORXONALARI RAHBARI VA MUTAXASSISLARINI MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI BO‘YICHA O‘QITISH VA BILIMLARINI SINOVDAN O‘TKAZISHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH// INTELLEKT. MONOGRAFIYA.2023
44. Dustkabilovich, R. O. & o`g`li, M. S. H. (2021). Innovative Technologies in Teachingdirectors and Specialists of Industrial Enterprises on "Labor Protection". *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 80-85. Retrieved from <http://ejlss.indexedresearch.org/index.php/ejlss/article/view/3>
45. Rakhimov Oktyabr Dustkabilovich; Muradov Sirojiddin Husan o`g`li. Innovative Technologies in Teachingdirectors and Specialists of Industrial Enterprises on "Labor Protection"// *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 2021/12/29. 80-85.
46. Muradov S.H; Safarov Sh. O‘. MEHNAT SHAROITLARI VA MUHITINI “KAIZEN” USULI YORDAMIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING INNOVATSION YECHIMLARI// PAXTA TOZALASH, TO‘QIMACHILIK VA YENGIL SANOAT SOHALARINING TECHNOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. 2023. 90-92
47. СИРОЖИДДИН МУРАДОВ. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ОХРАНА ТРУДЫ НА ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ КОРЕИ// ХӨДӨЛМӨР, НИЙГМИЙН ХАРИЛЦАА СУДЛАЛ. 2023. 242-247
48. Muradov Sirojiddin Husan ugli; Odilov Muzaffar. MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY// *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHERS*0 2023. 201-206
49. Sultonova D. N., qizi Siddiqova M. A. COLOR SCHEME IN THE FORMATION OF THE ARTISTIC ENVIRONMENT OF THE INTERIOR OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL CENTERS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 109-115.
50. Muradov, S., & Usmonov H. (2024). MEHNATNI MUHOFAZA QILISHNING RIVOJLANISH TARIXIY BOSQICHLARINI O‘RGANISH. *Interpretation and*

Researches.

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от

<https://interpretationandresearches.uz/index.php/iar/article/view/1915>

51. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН учитель-стажер. Каршинский инженерно-экономический институт кафедры «Охрана труда и техника безопасности» Республики Узбекистан. (2024). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10684166>
52. СИРОЖИДДИН М. НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 167-177.
53. Muradov S. CONSTRUCTION-INSTALLATION ISHLARIDA KUTARAMA KRANLARDAN USE FUNDAMENTAL SECURITY OF SUPPLY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 786-792.
54. Muradov, S. (2024). CONSTRUCTION-INSTALLATION ISHLARIDA KUTARAMA KRANLARDAN USE FUNDAMENTAL SECURITY OF SUPPLY. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 786–792. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29479>
55. Muradov, S. (2024). ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING KTZM. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(2), 1142–1152. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10701651>
56. СИРОЖИДДИН, МУРАДОВ. "РАЖАБОВ ХУРШИД ФАХРИДДИН ЎҒЛИ. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 10 (2023): 27.
57. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 42-47.
58. Muradov S. PRINCIPLES OF ENSURING THE SAFETY OF USING LIFTING CRANES IN CONSTRUCTION-ASSEMBLY WORKS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 933-939.
59. Muradov S. ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING KTZM //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1142-1152.
60. Muradov S., Usmonov H. MEHNATNI MUHOFAZA QILISHNING RIVOJLANISH TARIXIY BOSQICHLARINI O 'RGANISH //Interpretation and researches. – 2024.
61. СИРОЖИДДИН М. НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 167-177.

62. Muzaffar O. MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY Muradov Sirojiddin Husan ugli.
63. Muradov Sirojiddin Husan ugli; Odilov Muzaffar. MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY// [International journal of scientific researchers](#). 2023. 201-206
64. Мурадов С. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5.
65. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 42-47.
66. Muradov S. CONSTRUCTION-INSTALLATION ISHLARIDA KUTARAMA KRANLARDAN USE FUNDAMENTAL SECURITY OF SUPPLY //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 786-792.
67. Фойдаланиш Қ. М. И. К. К., АСОСЛАРИ Х. Т. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH //MODERN SCIENCE. – 2024. – Т. 2181. – С. 3906.
68. Muradov S. ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING KTZM //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1142-1152.
69. КИМҶОВИҶ К. Қ. О. Л. О. А., ВАҲОЛАШ Н. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH //MODERN SCIENCE. – 2024. – Т. 2181. – С. 3906.
70. КИМҶОВИҶ К. Қ. О. Л. О. А., ВАҲОЛАШ Н. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH //MODERN SCIENCE. – 2024. – Т. 2181. – С. 3906.
71. Фойдаланиш Қ. М. И. К. К., АСОСЛАРИ Х. Т. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH //MODERN SCIENCE. – 2024. – Т. 2181. – С. 3906.
72. Muradov S. ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING KTZM //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1142-1152.
73. КИМҶОВИҶ К. Қ. О. Л. О. А., ВАҲОЛАШ Н. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH //MODERN SCIENCE. – 2024. – Т. 2181. – С. 3906.
74. КИМҶОВИҶ К. Қ. О. Л. О. А., ВАҲОЛАШ Н. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH //MODERN SCIENCE. – 2024. – Т. 2181. – С. 3906.
75. Фойдаланиш Қ. М. И. К. К., АСОСЛАРИ Х. Т. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH //MODERN SCIENCE. – 2024. – Т. 2181. – С. 3906.
76. Muradov, S. (2024). ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING STRONG TOXIC SUBSTANCES (KTZM). MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(3), 464–472. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1082809>
77. Muradov, S. (2024). CHEMICAL STATUS ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(3), 455–463. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10828083>

78. Muradov, S. (2024). STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF WORKING ACCIDENTS. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(3), 444–454. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10828055>
79. Muradov, S. (2024). MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(3), 473–484. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10828837>
80. Muradov, S. (2024). INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(3), 485–492. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10828873>
81. Muradov, S. (2024). ENSURING SAFETY OF WORKERS IN CONSTRUCTION. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(3), 493–501. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10828960>
82. 1MURADOV SIROJIDDIN HUSAN O'GLI Intern-teacher of the Department of "Labor Protection and Technical Safety" of the Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics, & ESHPO'LATOV AZIZBEK ADHAM O'GLI 4 nd year student of the Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics, "Labor Protection and Technical Safety" Karshi, Uzbekistan. (2023). PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HYGIENE BASIS OF HUMAN LABOR ACTIVITY. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10148671>
83. Мурадов С. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5.
84. Мурадов Сирожиддин. (2023). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ. International Journal of Advanced Research in Education, Technology and Management, 2(5), 260–270. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7976908>
85. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 42-47.
86. Muradov Sirojiddin Intern-teacher of the Department of "Labor Protection and Technical Safety" of the Institute of Engineering Economy of Karshi, & Egamberdiyev Umurzoq 4 nd year student of the Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics, "Labor Protection and Technical Safety Karshi city, Uzbekistan. (2023). INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10416639>
87. MURADOV SIROJIDDIN HUSAN O'GLI. (2023). ANALYSIS OF "MEASURES TO ENSURE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY IN THE FIELD OF CARGO TRANSPORTATION AND LOADING.". <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8434940>
88. Muradov S. H. Safarov Sh. O ‘. MEHNAT SHAROITLARI VA MUHITINI “KAIZEN” USULI YORDAMIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING INNOVATSION YECHIMLARI //PAXTA TOZALASH, TO ‘QIMACHILIK VA YENGIL SANOAT SOHALARINING TEXNOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. – 2023. – С. 90-92.

89. Muradov S. H. o‘g‘li, & Zayniyev, UU o‘g‘li.(2023). PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – T. 2. – №. 14. – С. 116-119.
90. Husan o‘g‘li M. S., Shavkat o‘g‘li E. D. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – С. 11-17.
91. Muradov S. H. o‘g‘li, & Egamov , D. S. o‘g‘li. (2023). INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(14 SPECIAL), 340–342. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/4443>
92. O‘G E. L. A. A. et al. PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HYGIENE BASIS OF HUMAN LABOR ACTIVITY //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 11.
93. Muradov, S. (2024). ENSURING SAFETY OF WORKERS IN CONSTRUCTION. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 493–501. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30193>
94. Muradov S. ENSURING SAFETY OF WORKERS IN CONSTRUCTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 493-501.
95. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН учитель-стажер. Каршинский инженерно-экономический институт кафедры «Охрана труда и техника безопасности» Республики Узбекистан. (2024). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10684166>
96. Muradov, S. . (2024). CHEMICAL STATUS ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 455–463. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30167>
97. Muradov S. CHEMICAL STATUS ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 455-463.
98. Muradov, S. (2024). INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD. Modern Science and Research, 3(2), 485–492. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30192>
99. Muradov S. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 485-492.
100. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 42-47.

101. Muradov, S. (2024). MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 473–484. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30191>
102. Muradov S. MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY // *Modern Science and Research*. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 473-484.
103. Muradov S. ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING STRONG TOXIC SUBSTANCES (KTZM) // *Modern Science and Research*. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 464-472.
104. Muradov S. CHEMICAL STATUS ASSESSMENT AND ANALYSIS // *Modern Science and Research*. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 455-463.
105. Muradov, S. (2024). ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING STRONG TOXIC SUBSTANCES (KTZM). *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 464–472. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30168>
106. Muradov, S. (2024). STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF WORKING ACCIDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 444–454. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/30166>
107. Muradov S. STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF WORKING ACCIDENTS // *Modern Science and Research*. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 444-454.
108. Muradov, S. (2024). ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING KTZM. *MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH*, 3(2), 1142–1152. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10701651>
109. Sirojiddin M. KTZM QO ‘LLANILADIGAN OBYEKTlardagi AVARIYADA KIMYOVIY HOLATNI BAHOLASH. – 2024.
110. Sirojiddin, Muradov. "KTZM QO ‘LLANILADIGAN OBYEKTlardagi AVARIYADA KIMYOVIY HOLATNI BAHOLASH." (2024).
111. Muzaffar O. MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY Muradov Sirojiddin Husan ugli.
112. СИРОЖИДДИН учитель-стажер, М. У. Р. А. Д. О. В. "Каршинский инженерно-экономический институт кафедры «Охрана труда и техника безопасности» Республики Узбекистан.(2024). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ. Zenodo." *НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ*.
113. СИРОЖИДДИН учитель-стажер, М. У. Р. А. Д. О. В. Каршинский инженерно-экономический институт кафедры «Охрана труда и техника безопасности» Республики Узбекистан.(2024). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ. Zenodo. *НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ*.
114. Muradov, S. (2024). ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING KTZM. *MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH*, 3(2), 1142–1152. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10701651>